

1 **Metagenomics and stable isotope probing reveal the complementary contribution of fungal and**
2 **bacterial communities in the recycling of dead biomass in forest soil**

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11 **Abstract**

12 Forest soils represent important terrestrial carbon (C) pools, where C is primarily fixed in plant biomass
13 and then is incorporated in the biomass of fungi and bacteria. Although classical concepts assume that
14 fungi are the main decomposers of the recalcitrant organic matter within plant and microbial biomass,
15 whereas bacteria are considered to mostly utilize simpler compounds, recent studies have shown that
16 fungi and bacteria overlap in substrate utilization. Here, we studied the microbial contribution to the
17 recycling of dead biomass by analyzing the bacterial and fungal communities in soil microcosms
18 supplemented with ¹³C-labeled biomass of plant, fungal, and bacterial origin using a combination of DNA-
19 stable isotope probing and metagenomics. Both fungi and bacteria contributed actively to the degradation
20 of complex components of plant and microbial biomass. Specific families of carbohydrate-active enzymes
21 (CAZyme) were involved in the degradation of each biomass type. Moreover, the analysis of five bacterial
22 metagenome-assembled genomes indicated the key role of some bacterial genera in the degradation of
23 plant biomass (*Cytophaga* and *Asticcacaulis*) and microbial biomass (*Herminiimonas*). The enzymatic

24 systems utilized by bacteria are highly complex and complementary but also highly diverse among taxa.
25 The results confirm the importance of bacteria, in addition to fungi, as decomposers of complex organic
26 matter in forest soils.

27 Keywords: decomposition, forest soil, microbial community, CAZyme, SIP-metagenomic, dead biomass

28

29 **1. Introduction**

30 Forests represent some of the most important carbon (C) pools and sinks on Earth. Since nearly half of
31 the C stored in these ecosystems is contained in soils, understanding the processes involved in C cycling
32 in forest soils is essential in the current context of global climate change (Pan et al., 2011). Microorganisms
33 are the main players involved in the recycling and turnover of soil organic matter. As such, they contribute
34 largely to the C flow in this habitat and have the potential to influence the feedback between climate and
35 the global C cycle (Schimel and Schaeffer, 2012). Therefore, predicting how forests will respond to future
36 environmental conditions is impossible without understanding the roles of soil microbes in C cycling
37 (Graham et al., 2016; Trivedi et al., 2013).

38 The major sources of forest soil C are comprised of the C allocated by tree roots into soil and of the C
39 contained in the dead plant biomass in the forms of litter and dead wood. This dead plant biomass is
40 composed mostly of cellulose, hemicelluloses and lignin, forming a complex and recalcitrant matrix
41 (Bomble et al., 2017). Microbial biomass represents another important pool of organic matter whose fate
42 in the soil is far less understood. Forest soils are rich in ectomycorrhizal (ECM) and saprotrophic fungi and
43 the decomposition of dead mycelia represents an important process for the cycling of C and other
44 nutrients in these ecosystems (Ekblad et al., 2013; Fernandez and Koide, 2014). Dead fungal biomass is
45 composed mainly of polysaccharides that can make up 80-90% of the total cell wall, but it also contains
46 lipids and mannoproteins (Baldrian et al., 2013b; Fesel and Zuccaro, 2016; Free, 2013). The main

47 components of the polysaccharide fraction include chitin, a polymer of *N*-acetylglucosamine units,
48 different types of beta- and alpha-glucans, glucomannans and galactomannans. Dead bacterial biomass is
49 considered to be equally abundant in forest soils, showing higher turnover rates than fungal biomass
50 (Gunina et al., 2017). The composition of cell walls is highly diverse in bacteria (Silhavy et al., 2010).
51 Peptidoglycan (PG), a polymer of *N*-acetylglucosamine and *N*-acetylmuramic acid units connected to
52 chains of amino acids, is a major and universal component of bacterial cell walls (Egan et al., 2017;
53 Scheffers and Pinho, 2005). In gram-positive bacteria, PG is densely functionalized with other polymers.
54 Cell-wall glycopolymers such as teichoic, teichuronic and teichulosonic acids, which are attached either to
55 the PG or to membrane lipids, are the most abundant (Brown et al., 2013; Schaffer and Messner, 2005;
56 Weidenmaier and Peschel, 2008). Apart from PG and cell-wall glycopolymers, the bacterial cell wall
57 includes proteins, glycosyl 1-phosphates and other sugar-containing polymers such as arabinogalactan,
58 lipomannan and lipoarabinomannan (Hamedi and Poorinmohammad, 2017). Furthermore, gram-negative
59 bacteria contain lipopolysaccharides and lipoproteins in their outer membranes (Silhavy et al., 2010).
60 Many bacteria also produce a range of chemically different extracellular polysaccharides, which can be
61 utilized as C sources by other microorganisms in soils (Bazaka et al., 2011; Mishra and Jha, 2013; Wang et
62 al., 2015).

63 The turnover of carbohydrates in plant and microbial biomass can be tracked by analyzing the microbial
64 enzymes that take part in the C turnover—the carbohydrate-active enzymes (CAZymes) (Žifčáková et al.,
65 2017). CAZymes, classified into a hierarchy of families based on their structure and function, act on
66 oligosaccharides, polysaccharides and glycoconjugates (Lombard et al., 2014). Among the CAZymes,
67 glycoside hydrolases (GHs), which hydrolytically cleave the glycosidic bonds within carbohydrates or
68 between a carbohydrate and a noncarbohydrate moiety, are the most important in decomposition. In this
69 sense, cellulases, β -glucosidases and hemicellulases such as endoxylanases, β -xylosidases, xyloglucanases,
70 endomannanases, mannosidases, fucosidases, and arabinosidases from several GH families are the main

71 enzymes that degrade plant biomass (Bomble et al., 2017). Beside them, lytic polysaccharide
72 monoxygenases (LPMOs), classified as enzymes with auxiliary activities (AA) in the CAZy database, have
73 also been found to play an important role in the degradation of cellulose (Vaaje-Kolstad et al., 2017). In
74 addition, several AA families including peroxidase, oxidoreductase and laccase activities participate either
75 directly or indirectly in the degradation of lignin (Levasseur et al., 2013). Finally, carbohydrate esterases
76 (CEs) from several families participate in the decomposition of hemicelluloses. In the case of fungal
77 biomass, chitinases and N-acetylglucosaminidases from three GH families are involved in the degradation
78 of chitin, and glucanases from several GH families, which degrade glucans, are highlighted as main players
79 involved in its degradation. The lysozymes and PG lytic transglycosylases are important enzymes involved
80 in the degradation of PG in bacterial biomass. Catalytically active CAZymes may contain carbohydrate-
81 binding modules (CBMs), which are essential for effective hydrolysis because they mediate binding to
82 cellulose, xylan, chitin or other carbohydrates (Donohoe and Resch, 2015). Many GH families include
83 enzymes that are structurally similar but have wider substrate specificity, and associating one family to
84 the degradation of one type of compound is not always easy (Nguyen et al., 2018). Moreover, the
85 complex, diverse and not fully characterized composition of dead biomass in forest soils, especially in the
86 case of fungal and bacterial biomass, may entail the implication of more CAZyme families than those
87 currently proposed.

88 For a long time, fungi were assumed to be the major decomposers of complex organic matter in forest
89 soils due to their filamentous nature, which allows them to colonize substrates efficiently, their ability to
90 produce a rich battery of extracellular enzymes and their limited requirements of N, which is rather rare
91 in cell wall biopolymers. This assumption led to underestimation of the role of bacteria in decomposition,
92 and bacteria were typically expected to target simple substrates (de Boer et al., 2005; Rousk and Frey,
93 2015). Different studies have indicated that bacteria play a more important role in the transformation and
94 mineralization of organic matter and contribute significantly to decomposition in forest soils (Eichorst and

95 Kuske, 2012; Stursova et al., 2012; Verastegui et al., 2014). The high percentage of bacteria that potentially
96 decompose cellulose found in forest soil and the high frequency of genes involved in the degradation of
97 structural plant polysaccharides found in bacterial genomes support that the involvement of bacteria in
98 plant biomass decomposition is relatively common (Berlemont and Martiny, 2015; López-Mondéjar et al.,
99 2016a; Wilhelm et al., 2019). In addition, analyses of forest soil metatranscriptomes show significant
100 contribution of bacteria to CAZyme production (Hesse et al., 2015; Lladó et al., 2019; Žifčáková et al.,
101 2017). Moreover, Brabcova et al. (2016) showed that decomposing mycelium in forest soil presents
102 hotspots of bacterial abundance, maintaining bacterial over fungal decomposers. In our previous work,
103 we demonstrated that both fungi and bacteria are involved in the assimilation and mineralization of C
104 from complex sources existing in soil. In addition, we showed that fungi may be better suited for the
105 utilization of plant biomass, whereas most bacteria prefer microbial biomass (López-Mondéjar et al.,
106 2018).

107 The aim of this study was to describe the enzymatic toolbox used for the decomposition of various
108 biomass types by forest soil bacteria and fungi. To accomplish this, we prepared soil microcosms with the
109 addition of ¹³C-labeled biomass of plant, fungal, and bacterial origin. We used DNA-SIP and metagenomics
110 to analyze the enzymatic tools of microbial decomposers. We hypothesized that although the CAZyme
111 pool will be different for each type of biomass, fungi and bacteria will encode similar CAZyme families
112 involved in the degradation of biomass of the same origin. Additionally, in line with the preference of fungi
113 for plant biomass, we hypothesized that the number of fungal CAZymes involved in the degradation of
114 plant biomass will be higher than the number of those targeting microbial biomass. Importantly, this study
115 also provides a comprehensive answer about the CAZyme families involved in the degradation of various
116 biomass types, including the involvement of minor CAZy families that might have been overlooked so far.

117 **2. Material and Methods**

118 2.1. Sample collection

119 Soil was collected from the organic horizon of a sessile oak (*Quercus petraea*) forest in the Xaverovský Háj
120 Natural Reserve in the Czech Republic. Previously, this site has been studied with respect to the
121 composition of microbial communities and their seasonal changes and the activity of extracellular
122 enzymes related to the decomposition process (Šnajdr et al., 2008, Baldrian et al., 2010; Baldrian et al.,
123 2013a, Voříšková et al., 2014, López-Mondéjar et al., 2015). This study used the samples collected
124 previously, which were incubated as described in the study of López-Mondéjar et al. (2018). Briefly, soil
125 was sieved and preincubated at 10 °C for 48h and allocated in 100-ml flasks containing 5 g of soil and 0.08
126 g of different ¹³C-labeled substrates: ¹³C-glucose (99 atom% ¹³C), ¹³C-cellulose (from *Zea mays*, 97 atom%
127 ¹³C), ¹³C-hemicellulose (from *Zea mays*, 97 atom% ¹³C), ¹³C-plant biomass (from ground maize leaves, 97
128 atom% ¹³C), ¹³C-bacterial biomass (from *Streptomyces* sp. PR6, prepared by cultivation in media with ¹³C-
129 glucose as sole C source) and ¹³C-fungal biomass (from *Phanerochaete velutina* PV29, prepared by
130 cultivation in media with ¹³C-glucose as sole C source). Microcosms were slightly moistened with water to
131 reach 60% water content and incubated at 10 °C in the dark for 3 weeks (21 days). After this, three
132 microcosms per treatment were harvested and the material was frozen at -80 °C, freeze-dried and stored
133 at -40 °C.

134 2.2. DNA extraction and sequencing

135 DNA was extracted with the FastDNA Spin Kit for Soil (MP Biomedicals) in triplicate and purified with the
136 GeneCean Turbo Kit. Three micrograms of total DNA was used for isopycnic centrifugation in a cesium
137 trifluoroacetate (CsTFA) solution to separate the labeled and unlabeled fractions, as shown in López-
138 Mondéjar et al. (2018). After centrifugation, the labeled fractions representing the ¹³C-DNA were pooled
139 for each microcosm. Due to the small amount of DNA recovered after centrifugation, the labeled DNA
140 from triplicates from the same substrate was also pooled, and the total DNA was used for metagenome

141 sequencing. DNA libraries were prepared using the KAPA Hyper Prep Kit (Roche) according the
142 manufacturer's instructions. Metagenome libraries were sequenced on an Illumina HiSeq 2000 to
143 generate 250-base paired-end reads. In total, eight metagenomes were sequenced, including the ¹³C-
144 labeled DNA isolated after 21 days of incubation of soil with ¹³C-substrate (glucose (GL), cellulose (CE),
145 hemicellulose (HE), plant biomass (PB), bacterial biomass (BB) and fungal biomass (FB) and the DNA from
146 the control microcosms (with no substrate addition) at both 0 (C1) after 21 (C2) days of incubation.

147 *2.3. Metagenome assembly*

148 Reads from all the metagenome libraries were processed together in the same way as originally described
149 in Žifčáková et al. (2016). Briefly, the reads were quality trimmed by removing adapters, filtered by base
150 call quality, and normalized. Errors were trimmed by removing low abundance fragments of high coverage
151 reads. The paired-end assembly of the remaining reads was performed with the Velvet assembler (v
152 1.2.10) (Zerbino and Birney, 2008) using odd k-mer lengths ranging from 33 to 63. Resulting assembled
153 contigs were merged using CD-HIT v4.6 (Li and Godzik, 2006; Fu et al., 2012) and minimus2 Amos v3.1.0
154 (Sommer et al. 2007). Sequence data of all contig sequences (whole metagenome) were deposited in the
155 MG RAST database under the dataset number mgs446518.

156 Annotation of contigs was performed using both MG RAST (Meyer et al., 2008) and an in-house fungal-
157 predicted protein database (FPPD), as described by Žifčáková et al. (2017). The taxonomic classification
158 for each contig was retrieved from that of the two databases which showed lower bitscore values of the
159 best hit.

160 *2.4. CAZyme annotation*

161 The annotation of CAZymes in the metagenome contigs was carried out after gene calling using the
162 pipeline dbCAN (Yin et al., 2012), followed by manual curation considering the alignments to the
163 sequences in the CAZy database (February 2018) (Table 1). To assess the abundance in the metagenome,

164 individual sequence reads from each sample were mapped onto contigs identified as CAZyme using
165 bowtie 2.2.1 (Langmead et al., 2009), with the default settings of end to end alignment—sensitive. Data
166 were expressed as: per base coverage = read count × read length/contig length to calculate gene
167 abundance, as previously described (Žifčáková et al., 2017). R software (RCoreTeam, 2019) was used for
168 statistical analysis. Differences in gene abundance in each metagenome and the controls were tested
169 using the exact Fisher test (Gharechahi and Salekdeh, 2018). Differences at $P < 0.05$ were considered
170 statistically significant.

171 2.5. Recovery and analysis of metagenome assembled genomes (MAGs)

172 The recovery of metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) was performed as follows. First, quality-
173 controlled reads (see earlier) were assembled into scaffolds using IDBA-UD (Peng et al., 2012). Second,
174 the scaffolds were assigned as eukaryotic or prokaryotic using the EUKREP pipeline (West et al., 2018). No
175 significant number of scaffolds was assigned as eukaryotic; hence, we did not attempt to recover the
176 eukaryotic bins. Prokaryotic scaffolds were binned using ABAWACA (<https://github.com/CK7/abawaca>),
177 Maxbin2 (Wu et al., 2015), MetaBAT2 (Kang et al., 2019), and CONCOCT (Alneberg et al., 2014) and further
178 refined with the DAS Tool refinement method (Sieber et al., 2018). Completeness and contamination
179 values for each bin were determined using CheckM (Parks et al., 2015). Bins were considered MAGs when
180 the quality score was above 50, as defined by Parks and collaborators (Parks et al., 2017). Briefly, this
181 quality score is defined by the percentage of completeness of a bin minus five times the percent
182 contamination. The taxonomy was assigned to MAGs using GTDB version v0.2.2 (Parks et al., 2018) and
183 the Microbial Genomes Atlas (MiGA) webserver (Rodriguez et al., 2018). MAGs were compared with all
184 available genomes of bacteria belonging to the same family using *anvi'o* v5.5 (Eren et al., 2015) and the
185 average nucleotide identity (ANI) was calculated. Average amino acid identity (AAI) was computed using
186 the CompareM (v0.0.23) AAI workflow (D. H. Parks, unpublished materials,

187 <https://github.com/dparks1134/CompareM>). The CAZyme content of these genomes was predicted using
188 dbCAN2 (Zhang et al., 2018) followed by manual curation using the CAZy database.

189 **3. Results**

190 *3.1. Total diversity of the CAZyme pool in the metagenome*

191 In total, 132,197 CAZymes were identified from the 7.2 million predicted proteins of the whole
192 metagenome (1.84% of genes), of which 26.0% and 42.6% were assigned to bacteria and fungi,
193 respectively, and the rest (31.4%) were unassigned. The bacterial CAZymes belonged to 233 families,
194 including 95 GHs, 4 AAs, 14 CEs, 17 Polysaccharide Lyases (PLs), 49 CBMs and 54 GlycosylTransferases
195 (GTs), and the fungal CAZymes were assigned to 209 families, including 84 GHs, 10 AAs, 11 CEs, 9 PLs, 32
196 CBMs and 63 GTs (Fig. S1, S2, S3 and S4). Bacterial GHs accounted for 9.1% of all CAZymes with the highest
197 diversity in the families GH13 (amylase/ α -glucosidase/trehalase), GH109 (α -N-acetylgalactosaminidase),
198 GH3 (β -glucosidase), GH23 (lysozyme/ peptidoglycan lytic transglycosylase) and GH15
199 (glucoamylase/glucodextranase). Fungal GHs accounted for 16.2% of all CAZymes. Similar to bacteria,
200 GH3, GH13 and GH15 were the most diverse families, in addition to GH43 (β -xylosidase/endoxyranase)
201 and GH31 (α -glucosidase/ α -xylosidase). The number of fungal genes encoding AAs and CEs was twice as
202 high (1.7 and 8.5%, respectively) as bacterial genes (0.5 and 4.5%), but similar for PLs (0.3 vs 0.4%), GTs
203 (7.7 vs 8.1%) and CBMs (2.7 vs 2.7%).

204 In general, most of the fungal CAZymes were assigned to Ascomycota (55.9%), Basidiomycota (21.2%) and
205 Mucoromycota (9.3%). Among them, Ascomycota showed a higher number of contigs encoding GHs, AAs,
206 CBMs, CEs, PLs and GTs (Fig. 1). In the case of bacteria, the contigs encoding CAZymes were mainly
207 assigned to Proteobacteria (28.4%), Actinobacteria (25.7%), Acidobacteria (20.3%) and Bacteroidetes
208 (16.4%). These four phyla also showed the highest numbers of CAZymes of all six classes (Fig. 1).

209 *3.2. CAZyme pools in the fungal and bacterial communities*

210 Relative abundances of genes assigned to CAZyme families in the ^{13}C -enriched metagenomic DNA from
211 microcosms containing ^{13}C -supplemented substrates were compared with the abundance in the
212 metagenome of the control samples individually. In total, the percentage of CAZyme families that were
213 significantly increased in at least one of the ^{13}C -supplemented treatments was higher in fungi (69%) than
214 in bacteria (49%) (Fig. 2, Fig. 3). The increase in the relative abundance of certain CAZy families may
215 indicate a relative increase in the abundance of microorganisms utilizing carbon from certain sources.
216 When ^{13}C -cellulose was added to the soil, more CAZyme families were enriched in the fungal community
217 than in the bacterial community (24 vs 18, respectively). On the other hand, the bacterial community
218 showed more CAZyme families increasing upon the addition of ^{13}C -fungal biomass (52 vs 39) and ^{13}C -
219 bacterial biomass (52 vs 37). For ^{13}C -plant biomass and ^{13}C -hemicellulose, the numbers were similar for
220 bacteria and fungi; 52 and 53 in plant biomass, 67 and 69 in hemicellulose, respectively.

221 Both fungal and bacterial communities were enriched in numerous CAZymes known to be involved in the
222 degradation of plant, fungal and bacterial biomass (Fig. 2, Fig. 3). The CAZyme pool in the plant and
223 microbial dead biomass metagenomes was composed of numerous well-known fungal- and bacterial-
224 encoded CAZyme families including cellulases, glucosidases, xylanases, xylosidases, mannosidases,
225 galactosidases, glucanases, xyloglucanases, glucuronidases, chitinases, hexosaminidases, lysozymes,
226 acetyl xylan esterases and CBMs binding several polysaccharides.

227 *3.3. CAZyme families involved in the degradation of plant, fungal and bacterial biomass*

228 Although many of the CAZyme families were significantly increased in all of the ^{13}C metagenomes (Fig. 2,
229 Fig. 3), several of them were only enriched in a specific type of dead biomass (Fig. 4, Fig. 5). In general,
230 the fungal community contained a richer set of CAZyme families that were specifically increased upon the
231 addition of ^{13}C -labeled plant biomass and its components. The bacterial community also contained several

232 CAZyme families that increased after the addition of plant biomass, but this community was particularly
233 rich in CAZymes that increased after the addition of ¹³C-labeled bacterial and fungal biomass.

234 Regarding the fungal CAZymes involved in the degradation of plant biomass, we found several families
235 encoding enzymes that degrade cellulose and hemicelluloses (Fig. 4). In this sense, CAZyme families
236 containing β -glucosidases (GH1 and GH3), endoglucanases (GH5, GH9, and GH45), cellobiohydrolases
237 (GH7), endoxylanases (GH10 and GH11), other hemicellulases (GH62, GH67 and GH131), LPMOs and
238 oxidases (AA1, AA7 and AA9), and CBM families binding to plant biomass components (CBM1, CBM6,
239 CBM20, CBM21) increased in abundance when plant biomass, cellulose or hemicellulose were added to
240 soil. Interestingly, we found other families that were not related to the degradation of plant biomass and
241 their components, but encoding chitinases, glucanases, chitosanases or glucanosyltransferases (e.g.
242 GH72, GH75, GH79) and binding to chitin (CBM5 and CBM18). In the bacterial community, plant biomass
243 amended soil was enriched in different CAZy families than those of fungi (Fig. 5). Although most of the
244 families are also known to be involved in plant polysaccharide degradation, such as those encoding
245 endoglucanases (GH5 and GH9), β -glucosidases (GH116), endomannanases (GH26), endoxylanases
246 (GH30), xyloglucanases (GH44 and GH115), acetyl xylan esterases (CE2, CE4, CE7, CE8, CE14 and CE15)
247 and CBMs binding cellulose (CBM3), the rest of the CAZymes belonged to families that have not been
248 shown to participate in plant biomass degradation. The families GH4 (α -galactosidase/ 6-phospho- β -
249 glucosidase/ maltose-6-phosphate glucosidase), GH109 (α -N-acetylgalactosaminidase), AA6 (1,4-
250 benzoquinone reductase) and the domains CBM32 (binding to D-galactose and N-acetyl-D-galactosamine)
251 and CBM50 (binding to N-acetylglucosamine) were abundant in the metagenome.

252 Meanwhile, most of the fungal CAZymes enriched in ¹³C-bacterial biomass were assigned to families with
253 potential activity in bacterial biomass degradation. The roles of several families of bacterial CAZymes in
254 the decomposition of bacterial biomass are still unclear (Fig. 4, Fig. 5). Regarding the degradation of ¹³C-
255 fungal biomass, both bacterial and fungal CAZymes belonged to several families with uncertain roles in

256 the process, such as the family GH32, whose abundance increased in both the fungal and bacterial
257 communities.

258 3.4. Bacterial taxa and CAZymes degrading the main types of dead biomass in forest soil

259 Six MAGs were obtained from the metagenomes, but only 5 of them showed acceptable quality for further
260 analyses (Table S1). Four MAGs belonged to Proteobacteria, and the other two belonged to Bacteroidetes.
261 Since databases only classified the MAGs up to the family level, we compared MAGs with the available
262 genomes in the respective family. The results showed that MAG_2 and MAG_6 were most similar to
263 *Asticcacaulis benevestitus* DSM 16100 (76.3% and 75.9% ANI, respectively), *Asticcacaulis biprosthecium*
264 C19 (75.11% and 75.0% ANI, respectively) and *Asticcacaulis excentricus* CB 48 (74.58% and 74.15% ANI,
265 respectively) (Fig. S5). MAG_3 showed the highest similarity to *Cytophaga aurantiaca* DSM 3654 (77.25%
266 ANI) and to *Cytophaga hutchinsonii* ATCC 33406 (75.67% ANI) (Fig. S6). MAG_4 and MAG_5 showed the
267 highest similarity to *Herminiimonas arsenicoxydans* DSM 17148 (73.35% and 73.52% ANI, respectively)
268 and to *Collimonas fungivorans* NCCB 100033 (73.06% and 73.07% ANI, respectively) (Fig. S7). The same
269 similarity results were found when calculating the AAI values for all the MAGs (Supplementary File S1).

270 MAG_2, MAG_3 and MAG_6 showed the highest abundance on ¹³C-plant biomass, while MAG_4 and
271 MAG_5 were most abundant in the ¹³C-bacterial biomass metagenome (Fig. S8). These results
272 corresponded with the composition of their CAZyme gene sets (Table S2). For example, MAG_3 presented
273 numerous genes of families involved in plant biomass degradation, such as endoglucanases (GH9: 5 genes,
274 GH5: 4 genes), hemicelluloses (GH26: 2 genes, GH30: 2 genes, GH44: 1 gene, GH74: 2 genes) and xylan
275 esterases (CE2: 1 gene, CE4: 6 genes and CE14:1 gene). The CAZyme composition of the other two MAGs
276 abundant in plant biomass amended soil was different. Both MAG_2 and MAG_6 also encoded genes of
277 the GH9 (one gene each) and GH5 (two genes each) families and CEs, although to a lesser extent than
278 MAG_3. However, both genomes contained several genes belonging to the hemicellulolytic families, such

279 as GH39 (1 and 2 genes), GH42 (1 and 2 genes), GH51 (3 genes), GH67 (1 gene) and GH115 (2 genes),
280 which were not detected in MAG_3. MAG_4 and MAG_5 increased upon bacterial biomass addition, and
281 none of the CAZyme families with known involvement in bacterial biomass degradation were found, with
282 the exception of GH108 (lysozyme) in MAG_4. On the other hand, MAG_4 and MAG_5 contained genes
283 from the families GH36 (α -galactosidase), GH73 (peptidoglycan hydrolase with endo- β -N-
284 acetylglucosaminidase specificity) and GH94 (phosphorylases), which were highly enriched in the ^{13}C -
285 bacterial biomass metagenome (approximately 2 and 5 times higher abundance than in ^{13}C -plant biomass
286 (Fig. 3). Interestingly, other families only found in the ^{13}C -bacterial biomass metagenome, such as GH39
287 (β -xylosidase/ α -L-arabinofuranosidase) and GH105 (unsaturated glucuronyl/galacturonyl hydrolase),
288 were present in the genomes of MAG_2 and MAG_6, despite these bins were not abundant in the BB
289 metagenome.

290

291 **4. Discussion**

292 Using DNA-SIP and metagenomics, our study revealed that fungi and bacteria that utilize C from plant and
293 microbial biomass possess numerous CAZymes involved in the degradation of both types of biomass. This
294 finding supports the recent view that the roles of fungi and bacteria as primary consumers of complex
295 substrates are important (Kramer et al., 2016; Rousk and Frey, 2015; Žifčáková et al., 2017).

296 Despite the possibility that fungal CAZyme predictions in metagenomes are underestimated due to introns
297 in sequences, which make gene calling less reliable (Fierer et al., 2012; Pold et al., 2016), we still found
298 that the number of CAZymes assigned to fungi was larger than that of bacteria. The presence and
299 abundance of numerous well-known families encoding cellulases and hemicellulases in bacteria confirm
300 their role in the degradation of plant-derived biomass. These results add to the list of previous evidence
301 on the active contribution of bacteria in the decomposition of cellulose and hemicellulose (López-

302 Mondéjar et al., 2016a; Stursova et al., 2012; Wilhelm et al., 2019) and confirm that the increase in labeled
303 bacterial biomass after incubation is due to the actual degradation of plant biomass by hydrolytic enzymes
304 and not just a result of mutualistic feeding by cross-feeders in SIP experiments (López-Mondéjar et al.,
305 2018).

306 Contrary to our first hypothesis, the pool of CAZymes for degrading the diverse types of biomass was
307 distinct in fungi and bacteria. In this sense, some CAZyme families seem to be specific for the
308 decomposition of plant biomass and its components in fungi and others in bacteria. While bacteria contain
309 more esterases, fungi possess more oxidases, laccases and monooxygenases. The presence of these
310 complex fungal enzymatic systems for degrading plant biomass, which include not only GHs but also
311 LPMOs, may explain why fungi seem better suited to utilize plant-derived compounds (López-Mondéjar
312 et al., 2018). Bacteria contained more CBMs than fungi, which points at the importance of substrate
313 binding. Unlike fungi that produce mostly extracellular enzymes, cell-bound enzymes play a more
314 important role in the degradation of organic matter in soil bacteria (Lasa et al., 2019). Therefore, the
315 presence of CBMs in bacterial lytic enzymes allows the direct association of the bacterial cell with the
316 target polysaccharide, improving the efficacy of the lytic enzymes and increasing the competitive
317 exclusion of non-cellulolytic opportunists (Donohoe and Resch, 2015). Interestingly, after the addition of
318 plant biomass and its components, fungi also showed high abundance of specific CBM families assigned
319 to chitin- and glucan-binding (typical fungal cell wall components), which, however, were not increased
320 in the fungal biomass metagenome. Moreover, the addition of these plant-derived substrates also
321 increased the abundance of GHs from families potentially encoding chitinases, glucanases, chitosanases
322 and glucanosyltransferases (such as GH18, GH71, GH72 and GH75). The abundance of fungal enzymes
323 that target and bind to fungal cell wall components may indicate a strong competition among fungi for
324 plant-derived substrates. These competitive fungal-fungal interactions for resources among different
325 taxonomic groups often occur in soils (Boddy and Hiscox, 2016; Woodward and Boddy, 2008), which is

326 especially important between different fungal guilds (Fernandez and Kennedy, 2016). The fact that these
327 families were not increased in the fungal biomass metagenome may be explained by the differences in
328 the attractivity of the living and dead fungal biomass as a target for attack, such as the nutrient content
329 or the presence of secondary compounds (Fernandez et al., 2016) and by the reportedly minor role of
330 fungi in the decomposition of dead fungal biomass (Brabcova et al., 2016; López-Mondéjar et al., 2018).

331 In accordance with our second hypothesis, we demonstrated that fungal communities encode more
332 specific CAZymes that degrade plant biomass, while bacterial communities are richer in CAZymes that
333 target microbial biomass. As mentioned above, when cellulose was added to soil more fungal CAZymes
334 were increased, including not only endoglucanases as in the bacterial community but also LPMOs and
335 CBMs for cellulose binding. Similar results were presented by Žifčáková et al. (2017), who found that fungi
336 are the major producers of CAZymes involved in lignocellulose degradation in spruce forests, while the
337 transcription of CAZymes involved in the degradation of bacterial and fungal cell walls was increased in
338 bacteria. Our results are in accordance with previous studies supporting the role of fungi as the agents
339 primarily responsible for the transformation of plant-derived carbon in terrestrial ecosystems and
340 reinforce the evidence that bacteria are the main decomposers of mycelia in litter and soils (Bhatnagar et
341 al., 2018; Brabcova et al., 2016; Tláskal et al., 2016; Voříšková et al., 2014). Microbial biomass represents
342 a more readily decomposable substrate than lignocellulose, and bacteria have been shown to dominate
343 the initial phase of dead fungal biomass decomposition (Brabcová et al., 2018). As noted previously, the
344 different nitrogen content between microbial and plant biomass could explain the high abundance of
345 bacteria in the decomposition of microbial biomass (López-Mondéjar et al., 2018). Bacteria contain more
346 N in their biomass than fungi, and specialization to the decomposition of N-rich biomass may reflect their
347 higher nutritional demand (Wallenstein et al., 2006).

348 Linking genes to environmental processes is vital for understanding the role of microbes in ecosystems
349 (Graham et al., 2016). In the case of CAZyme families, it is possible to link genes with targeted substrates

350 and thus with a specific part of the soil decomposer food web (Nguyen et al., 2018). The links between
351 the CAZyme families, catalytic functions and substrates demonstrated here, were, however, not always
352 entirely clear. While as much as 70% of the CAZyme families that were enriched after addition of plant-
353 derived biomass are known to target plant biomass components, in the case of fungal or bacterial
354 biomass, the percentage of CAZyme families known to target them was smaller. Despite some CAZyme
355 families showing unique substrate specificity, most families have wide substrate specificity; moreover,
356 this substrate specificity is often unknown for several families (Nguyen et al., 2018). Although gene
357 enrichment after substrate addition may indicate the involvement of a gene product in the processing of
358 the substrate, none of the two highly abundant MAGs on bacterial biomass contained any of the known
359 BB-specific genes, while they contained other families such as GH73 and GH108, both encoding lysozymes.
360 Although these two families were enriched in bacterial biomass, they were not specific and appeared on
361 plant and fungal biomass amended soil. Previous studies using SIP showed that the degradation of some
362 bacterial components in soil is mainly carried out by bacteria with low identities to known species, mostly
363 from uncultured bacteria from the *Planctomycetes*, *Armatimonadetes* and the Candidate Phyla Radiation
364 (CPR) groups (Wang et al., 2015). Most of these taxa are still poorly represented in the databases with
365 only a low number of available sequences, which may hinder the biochemical characterization of the
366 genes potentially involved in the degradation of microbial biomass (Lloyd et al., 2018).

367 After demonstrating that bacteria incorporate significant amounts of C from dead plant biomass (López-
368 Mondéjar et al., 2018), the enrichment of bacterial CAZyme families targeting plant biomass that we
369 showed here confirms that bacteria indeed contribute to plant biomass degradation. Two potentially
370 different enzymatic systems for the degradation of plant biomass were observed across MAGs: the first
371 was represented by *Cytophaga* (MAG_3) and the second was represented by *Asticcacaulis* (MAG_2 and
372 MAG_6). Although some of the genes encoding hydrolytic enzymes were common, the genome of
373 *Cytophaga* contained more genes potentially encoding endoglucanase, endomannanase, endoxylanase

374 and xyloglucanase activities. *Asticcacaulis* contained fewer endoglucanases, but more genes encoding
375 debranching hemicellulases, such as glucuronidases, α -fucosidases, β -galactosidases, α -L-
376 arabinofuranosidase, β -glucosidases and β -xylosidases. In line with these differences, *Asticcacaulis* was
377 more abundant on hemicellulose. *Cytophaga* is a common cellulolytic soil bacterium that has a unique
378 mechanism for cellulose degradation (Lopez-Mondejar et al., 2019). As previously found by other authors,
379 the recovered genome did not contain any cellobiohydrolases or LPMOs, showing that the system for
380 cellulose degradation used by this bacterium is still poorly understood (Wang et al., 2017; Zhu et al., 2016).
381 *Asticcacaulis* spp. have been isolated from soils, and their utilization of cellulose has been demonstrated
382 using SIP (Eichorst and Kuske, 2012; Stursova et al., 2012). It was recently demonstrated that *Asticcacaulis*
383 assimilated ^{13}C from both cellulose and hemicellulose added to forest soil, indicating its high abundance
384 and its ability to adhere to lignocellulose, suggesting its role in the decomposition of cellulose and
385 hemicellulose (Wilhelm et al., 2019). Our previous results also showed that the genera *Asticcacaulis* and
386 *Cytophaga* are specialists utilizing plant-derived compounds. Both genera were abundant in the bacterial
387 community when ^{13}C -plant biomass or ^{13}C -cellulose was added to soil, while *Asticcacaulis* was also
388 abundant in samples with ^{13}C -hemicellulose (López-Mondéjar et al., 2018). The presence of structurally
389 variable enzymatic systems for decomposing cellulose and hemicellulose among different cellulolytic
390 bacteria has been previously reported in several taxa abundant in forest soils (López-Mondéjar et al.,
391 2016a; López-Mondéjar et al., 2016b). Here, the complementary nature of the two enzymatic systems of
392 these abundant and specialist bacterial taxa, one targeting the backbones and the other targeting the
393 branches of lignocellulose, confirm that in natural environments, plant biomass is degraded by the
394 cooperation of complex microbial communities rather than by a single species, as previously assumed
395 (Cragg et al., 2015, Cavaliere et al., 2017, López-Mondéjar et al., 2019).

396 Our results also indicate the importance of *Herminiimonas* in the degradation of dead microbial biomass,
397 which is used by this genus as a C source (López-Mondéjar et al., 2018). To date, only few species of this

398 genus have been described, mainly those isolated from water but also from urban and contaminated soils
399 (Koh et al., 2017; Sahin et al., 2010). Previous studies showed that *Herminiimonas* is abundant in forest
400 soils (Barta et al., 2017), where it accumulates C from cellulose and plant biomass (López-Mondéjar et al.,
401 2018; Stursova et al., 2012). This ability can be explained by the presence of several genes involved in
402 plant biomass degradation in the MAGs related to *Herminiimonas*, although in smaller numbers than in
403 the MAGs related to *Cytophaga* and *Asticcacaulis*. For example, three potential endoglucanases from
404 families GH9 and GH5 were found both in MAG_4 and MAG_5 but no endoxylanases or other
405 hemicellulose backbone-degrading enzymes. However, these genomes encoded numerous genes from
406 the families GH23, GH24, GH73 and GH108, potentially encoding lysozymes for degrading bacterial cell
407 walls, which may explain their enrichment after bacterial biomass addition. Moreover, both MAGs
408 contained genes encoding a β -1,2-glucanase from the family GH144, which is involved in the degradation
409 of glucans naturally present in some bacteria (Abe et al., 2017). Recently, *Herminiimonas* has been
410 reported to be involved in the degradation of mycelial necromass in forest soil (Sukdeo et al., 2019).
411 However, the analysis of our two genomes revealed only one (in MAG_5) and two (in MAG_4) genes
412 encoding for chitinases and no *N*-acetylglucosaminidases for chitin utilization; moreover, none of the CAZy
413 families enriched on fungal biomass were present. In accordance with our previous results,
414 *Herminiimonas* appears to be a generalist decomposer that is able to use substrates of various origins
415 (López-Mondéjar et al., 2018).

416 In summary, the current study confirms that both fungi and bacteria are involved in the recycling of dead
417 biomass in forest ecosystems and in the assimilation and mineralization of C of both plant and microbial
418 origin. In addition to the proven role of fungi in the decomposition of plant biomass, members of the
419 bacterial community appear to be important players in the degradation of plant-derived compounds by
420 using structurally variable enzymatic systems. Moreover, the complementary nature of these systems,
421 targeting the cellulose and hemicellulose backbones (such as *Cytophaga*) or preferentially focused on the

422 disassembly of hemicellulosic branches (such as *Asticcacaulis*), supports the existence of different
423 ecological niches for specialist cellulolytic bacteria and their potential synergy in the decomposition of
424 complex polysaccharides. Bacteria are also relevant members of the community involved in the
425 degradation of microbial dead biomass in forest soil, using enzymes that are still unknown. Unlike plant
426 biomass, composed mainly by cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin, the composition of microbial biomass
427 appears to be much more diverse and complex. The degradation of this pool of various polysaccharides
428 (glucans, mannans, chitin, or galactans) and glycoconjugates (glycopolymers, glycosyl phosphates or
429 glycoproteins) composing microbial cell walls has not yet been properly addressed and deserves further
430 attention. The importance of microbial biomass, its pool size and turnover rates in forest soils are also still
431 difficult to quantify (Brabcová et al., 2018; Ekblad et al., 2013), and understanding the fate of dead
432 microbial biomass in soils and its importance in C cycling deserves future attention as well. The results of
433 this study indicating specific roles of microbial taxa in C cycling improves our potential to develop models
434 of C cycling in terrestrial ecosystems and to improve the predictions about the fate of C in soils.

435

436 **Acknowledgements**

437 This work was supported by the Czech Science Foundation (18-26221Y) and by the project "BIOCEV -
438 Biotechnology and Biomedicine Centre of the Academy of Sciences and Charles University
439 CZ.1.05/1.1.00/02.0109" provided by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of CR and ERDF. We
440 acknowledge Petr Kohout for his help with the statistical analyses. The authors state that there is no
441 conflict of interest regarding the present manuscript.

442

443 **Figure legends**

444 **Figure 1.** Diversity of genes in the whole metagenome encoding CAZymes assigned to bacterial (A) and
445 fungal (B) phyla. GH: Glycoside Hydrolases, AA: Auxiliary Activities, CBM: Carbohydrate-Binding Modules,
446 CE: Carbohydrate Esterases, PL: Polysaccharide Lyases, GT: GlycosylTransferases.

447 **Figure 2.** Relative abundance of genes assigned to CAZyme families of fungi in the ^{13}C -incorporating
448 microbial community compared to the control. The values indicate fold enrichment in the ^{13}C -DNA of each
449 treatment / total DNA of control without substrate addition. Genes significantly more abundant in
450 treatment than in control are shown in yellow-red, genes significantly less abundant are shown in light
451 and dark blue, white squares indicate no significant difference between control and treatment.
452 Abbreviations indicate ^{13}C substrate addition of FB: fungal biomass; BB: bacterial biomass; PB: plant
453 biomass; CE: cellulose; and HE: hemicellulose. Only CAZy families with relative abundance significantly
454 different from control in at least one of the substrates are shown. Families containing enzymes degrading
455 cellulose or hemicellulose have a green mark, fungal biomass blue and bacterial biomass purple (source:
456 www.cazy.org).

457 **Figure 3.** Relative abundance of genes assigned to CAZyme families of bacteria in the ^{13}C -incorporating
458 microbial community compared to the control. The values indicate fold enrichment in the ^{13}C -DNA of each
459 treatment / total DNA of control without substrate addition. Genes significantly more abundant in
460 treatment than in control are shown in yellow-red, genes significantly less abundant are shown in light
461 and dark blue, white squares indicate no significant difference between control and treatment.
462 Abbreviations indicate ^{13}C substrate addition of FB: fungal biomass; BB: bacterial biomass; PB: plant
463 biomass; CE: cellulose; and HE: hemicellulose. Only CAZY families with relative abundance significantly
464 different from control in at least one of the substrates are shown. Families containing enzymes degrading
465 cellulose or hemicellulose have a green mark, fungal biomass blue and bacterial biomass purple (source:
466 www.cazy.org).

467 **Figure 4.** Fungal CAZyme families enriched after addition of each one of the different ^{13}C substrates: in
468 cellulose, in plant biomass or hemicellulose, in bacterial biomass, in fungal biomass and in both types of
469 microbial biomass and their known catalytic properties. Abundance represents the total number of
470 CAZymes of that family found in the whole metagenome. In bold, families showing activities directly
471 involved in the degradation of that substrate.

472 **Figure 5.** Bacterial CAZyme families enriched after addition of each one of the different ^{13}C substrates: in
473 cellulose, in plant biomass or hemicellulose, in bacterial biomass, in fungal biomass and in both types of
474 microbial biomass and their known catalytic properties. Abundance represents the total number of
475 CAZymes of that family found in the whole metagenome. In bold, families showing activities directly
476 involved in the degradation of that substrate.

477 **Table legend**

478 Table 1. List of the main CAZyme families encoding the enzymatic activities involved in the degradation of
479 several compounds presented in plant and microbial biomass according to CAZy (<http://www.CAZy.org>).

480 **Supplementary figures**

481 Fig. S1. Diversity of GH families in the whole metagenome. Data show the numbers of CAZyme genes in
482 each family. Bacterial CAZymes are in red, fungal CAZymes are in blue. Families containing genes involved
483 in the degradation of components of the plant biomass are marked in green, for fungal biomass in blue
484 and for bacterial biomass in purple (source: www.cazy.org).

485 Fig. S2. Diversity of AAs (A), CEs (B) and PLs (C) families of in the whole metagenome. Data show the
486 numbers of CAZyme genes in each family. Bacterial CAZymes are in red, fungal CAZymes are in blue.
487 Families containing genes involved in the degradation of components of the plant biomass are marked in
488 green, for fungal biomass in blue and for bacterial biomass in purple (source: www.cazy.org).

489 Fig. S3. Diversity of CBM families in the whole metagenome. Data show the numbers of CAZyme genes in
490 each family. Bacterial CAZymes are in red, fungal CAZymes are in blue. Families containing genes involved
491 in the degradation of components of the plant biomass are marked in green, for fungal biomass in blue
492 and for bacterial biomass in purple (source: www.cazy.org).

493 Fig. S4. Diversity of GT families in the whole metagenome. Data show the numbers of CAZyme genes in
494 each family. Bacterial CAZymes are in red, fungal CAZymes are in blue.

495 Fig. S5. Comparison of MAG_2 and MAG_6 with the genomes of the members of the family
496 Caulobacteraceae.

497 Fig. S6. Comparison of MAG_3 with the genomes of the members of the family Cytophagaceae.

498 Fig. S7. Comparison of MAG_4 and MAG_5 with the genomes of the members of the family
499 Oxalobacteraceae.

500 Fig. S8. Relative abundance of MAG sequences in the metagenomic DNA. Color codes indicate the relative
501 abundance of MAGs across samples. Abbreviations: C1 (control at t=0), C2 (control at t=3), FB (fungal
502 biomass), BB (bacterial biomass), PB (plant biomass), CE (cellulose), HE (hemicellulose), GL (glucose).

503 Supplementary Table S1. Taxonomy and properties of the six metagenome assembled genomes recovered
504 from the metagenomes generated in this study. Taxonomy and closest hit were generated by using GTDB,
505 MiGA and average nucleotide identity (ANI) comparison with available genomes in NCBI. Selected
506 genomic characteristics were generated by CheckM.

507 Supplementary Table S2. List of CAZymes (GHs, AAs, CEs, CBMs and PLs) encoded by MAGs. In color the
508 families which increased their abundance after addition of: plant biomass or their components (in green),
509 bacterial biomass (in purple), fungal biomass (in blue), or any type of microbial biomass (in pink).

510 Supplementary File S1. Amino acid identity (AAI) similarity between the MAGs and other genomes from
511 the same bacterial family. Bacterial genomes were obtained from NCBI. AAI was computed using the
512 CompareM AAI workflow.

513

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515

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